

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Evaluation of rice germplasm for some panicle and grain characteristics

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Collection, maintenance, and characterization of important traits are extremely useful to any crop breeding program. Many rice varieties were collected from different parts of the Casamance region in southern Senegal, and agronomic traits were characterized at Djibélór Agricultural Research Center.

Variations in panicle type, secondary ramification of panicle branches, lemma and palea pubescence, and grain awning

Table 1. Variability of panicle and grain traits of some rices from southern Senegal, expressed as varietal frequency on a 1-9 scale according to IBPGR-IRRI Rice Advisory Committee handbook.

Character	Varietal frequency on the scale								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Shattering			81		36				
Panicle fertility	128		74				12		
Endosperm type	110	100	4						

Table 2. Variability in 1,000-seed weight of rice from southern Senegal.

Character	Varietal frequency in the range								
	19	19.1- 21.0	21.1- 23.0	23.1- 25.0	25.1- 27.0	27.1-	29.1-	31.1-	33.1
1,000-seed wt	6	13	31	47	47	23			

were low. Variability in shattering, panicle fertility, endosperm type, and

1,000-seed weight is shown in Tables 1 and 2. *S*

Agronomic and yield characteristics of Topolea rices in western Romania

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We evaluated eight production-intensive Topolea rice lines in western Romania (Banloc rice fields). The lines have favorable, modern agronomic characteristics and were developed at IAS from local and introduced parents (Table 1). The lines were derived from hybrid combinations of three to four genotypes from different ecogeographic zones, including southwest Europe, southeast Europe, and northeast Asia.

All but Topolea 57-77, released in 1977, were released in 1976. Careful evaluation from 1979 to 1981 compared varietal performance with that of high-yielding local varieties Timis and Diamant. The new Topolea lines yielded higher (Table 2).

Topolea lines have semidwarf stature, with height ranging from 50 to 59 cm

Table 1. Topolea hybrid combinations, Banloc, Romania.

Line	Parentage	Year in control field
Topolea 57/17	Shin-Ei/Balila//Mimasari/Balila	1977
Topolea 58/76	Balico//Balila/Sesia 28 L.64///Krasnordar 424	1976
Topolea 60/76	Mimasari/Balila//Krasnordar 424	1976
Topolea 64/76	Shin-Ei/Balila//Krasnordar 424/Shin-Ei	1976
Topolea 66/76	Shin-Ei/Balila//Beco/Mantovo Vialone	1976
Topolea 70/76	Yuukara//Mimasari/Balila	1976
Topolea 71/76	Mimasari/Balila//G. Marchetti/Mantovo Vialone	1976
Topolea 88/76	Mimasari/Balila//Krasnordar 424/Shin-Ei	1976

Table 2. Yield and agronomic characteristics of Topolea lines, Banloc, Romania.

Line, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Panicle wt (g)	Duration (d)	Av yield 1979-80 (t/ha)
Topolea 57/77	56	13	122	1.8	113	8.4
Topolea 58/76	54	14	102	1.4	105	7.6
Topolea 60/76	59	14	120	2.1	119	8.6
Topolea 64/76	53	14	112	1.7	114	8.1
Topolea 66/76	53	13	150	2.3	121	8.0
Topolea 70/76	50	14	107	1.8	115	7.3
Topolea 71/76	58	15	157	2.0	123	7.7
Topolea 88/76	56	15	146	2.4	113	8.5
Av	55	14	127	1.9	115	8.0
Timis ^a 63	18		84	1.7	105	6.4
Diamanta	-	-	-	-	-	7.7

^aVarieties that are presently most productive. Diamant is the recently certified and approved variety.

(av 55 cm). Timis grows to 63 cm. The lines have short, dense, heavy panicles,

averaging 127 spikelets/panicle, each panicle weighing 1.9 g. Duration ranges

from 105 to 123 d and is shorter in tropical zones. Average yield is 8.5 t/ ha, versus 6.4 and 7.7 t/ ha for Timis and Diamant.

Topolea lines are lodging resistant, strongly resistant to cryptogamic diseases, and are N fertilizer responsive. *ℓ*

Complete slide sets of photos printed in Field problems of tropical rice, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

GRAIN QUALITY

Grain quality of hybrid indica rices in China

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About 8.8 million ha of irrigated land in China are planted to F₁ hybrids that yield 15-20% more than the best semidwarfs. Hybrids also produce high quality milled rice.

We evaluated 15 hybrid indica rice

and 2 semidwarfs for grain quality at CNRRI in 1984. Grain was harvested, dried to about 12% moisture content, and analyzed by IRRI methods.

Length width of milled hybrid rice ranged from 2.3 to 3.2, averaging 2.7 (see table). Grains were medium-long or long. Chalkiness varied widely. All hybrids except Wei You 35 had fewer opaque areas than the semidwarfs. Shan You 32 and Shan You 36 were slightly chalky.

Amylose content (AC) varied from

17% to 30% in 14 nonwaxy hybrid rices. Four hybrids, including Shan You 2 and Zhong You 2, had intermediate AC. Shan You 85 and Jun You 85 had low AC. The hybrids had intermediate to low gelatinization temperature (alkali spreading value of 4-7 in 1.7% KOH), and softer gel consistency. Shan You 2 had the best elongation ability (180%).

Analysis showed that most indica hybrids had better appearance and cooking and eating quality than the two commonly planted semidwarfs. *ℓ*

Quality analysis of 15 indica hybrid rices in China, 1984. ^a

Variety	Parentage	Milled rice			Chalkiness (scale)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value (scale)	Gel consistency (mm)	Grain elongation (%)
		Length (mm)	Width (mm)	(Length: width)					
Shan You 2	Zhen Shan 97A/IR24	57	24	2.4	5	22	6.0	36.5	180
Shan You 6	Zhen Shan 97A/IR26	59	24	2.5	5	27	6.0	39.0	170
Shan You 32	Zhen Shan 97A/IR32-5	73	23	3.2	1	26	6.5	36.0	150
Shan You 36	Zhen Shan 97A/IR36	59	24	2.5	1	25	6.0	35.5	160
Shan You 50	Zhen Shan 97A/IR50	58	22	2.6	3	31	6.0	39.5	160
Shan You 85	Zhen Shan 97A/Tai 8-5	65	23	2.8	5	17	5.0	41.5	150
Wei You 6	V20A/IR26	66	25	2.6	3	28	5.5	42.5	150
Wei You 35	V20A/Zhai Zao 26	60	23	2.6	7	22	5.0	44.0	150
Wei You 64	V20A/Ce 64	67	23	2.9	5	27	5.5	50.0	150
Wei You 98	V20A/T 0498	65	22	3.0	5	26	7.0	46.5	140
Xie You 64	Xie Qing Zao A/Ce 64	67	21	3.2	3	26	5.5	52.5	140
Zhang You 2	ZMY Y A/IR24	69	26	2.8	3	23	6.5	46.5	150
Jun You 85	Jun Xie A/Tai 8-5	58	24	2.4	5	17	5.0	50.5	160
Qing You Zao	Qing Si Ai A/Houmeizao	57	25	2.3	3	20	6.0	33.0	170
Mei You 85	Mei Nou A/Tai 8-5	63	23	2.7	Waxy	—	4.0	122.5	170
Zhen Zhu Ai 11	Nonhybrid	56	23	2.4	7	27	5.0	32.0	150
Gui Chao 2	Nonhybrid	48	27	1.8	7	26	5.0	30.5	150

^a Av of 2 replications.

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